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Polarographic Studies on the Reaction Between Manganese Sulphate and Sodium Mandelate

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It has been found that mandelic acid forms 1:1 chelates with number of metals¹⁻⁴ due to liberation of hydroxy as well as carboxylic protons of mandelic acid.

Polarographic studies of manganese (II) complexes with some ligands have been done⁵⁻⁸. Studies on Mn(II)-mandelate complex are reported here.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of Analar quality and the solutions were prepared by using double distilled water. The polarograms were recorded on Tinsley pen recording polarograph. The pH values of each set was determined by Philips pH meter. All the operations were done at room temperature.

The experimental solutions were made keeping potassium chloride, manganese sulphate and gelatin concentrations constant at 1M, 0.00125M and 0.001% respectively and the ligand (sodium-mandelate) concentration was varied up to 0.01125 M.

The polarograms of these samples were recorded after keeping the sets of solutions for 24 hr. and deoxygenating each set by passing purified hydrogen.

The half-wave potential $E_{1/2}$ of each polarogram was determined⁷, and then the change in half-wave potential $\Delta E_{1/2}$ with change in ligand concentration was plotted against $\Delta \log C_x$ (logarithm of change in ligand concentration). The number of ligand ions (P) that are co-ordinated with one metal ion was calculated using the following relation⁸.

$$\frac{\Delta E_{1/2}}{\Delta \log C_x} = -0.0591 \frac{P}{n}$$

and then the dissociation constant⁹ of the complex species by the following relation

$$(E_{1/2})_0 - (E_{1/2})_a = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log K_c - \frac{0.0591}{n} p \log C_x$$

The reversibility of the electrode reaction was verified by plotting $\log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$ against the corresponding potential

E where i_d = diffusion current and i = current at any applied potential E.

The plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ Vs $\Delta \log C_x$ for experimental data gives a straight line, the value of p was calculated and was found to be equal to one, indicating the formation of a 1:1 Mn(II)-mandelate complex. The value of the formation constant, K, is 1×10^4 (30° and $\mu = 1.0055$ to 1.055).

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Enthalpimetric Studies of Some Beryllium Complexes*

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CALORIMETRY provides a means for the direct measurement of enthalpy changes involved in complex forming reactions. Heat of reaction data for many metal ligand systems have been obtained from $\ln K$ vs $1/T$ plots (using sometimes only two temperatures). These are often of questionable validity since variations of $\ln K$ with temperature, in the intervals normally employed, are of the same order of magnitude as the uncertainties in the measurement of $\ln K$. Since, ΔH and not ΔG is a true measure of the metal ligand bond strength, the availability of reliable enthalpy values would lead to a better understanding of the factors affecting the strength of these bonds. The present paper describes the calorimetric measurement of enthalpy changes during the complexation of Be^{2+} with oxalate and malonate ions.

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